

GREEN SCENT

SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION
FOR A GREEN FUTURE

Project start date: 01/01/2022 | Duration: 36 months

D2.4 – GreenSCENT Policy Recommendations and Guidelines for Enhancing Environmental Citizenship in Education

Due date of the Deliverable: 30.06.2024

Actual submission date: 28.06.2024

Project	GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future
Call ID	H2020-LC-GD-2020-3-2020
Work Package	WP2 – Citizen Science and Co-Creation
Work Package Leader	VTT
Deliverable Leader	VTT
Deliverable coordinator	Teuvo Uusitalo teuvo.uusitalo@vtt.fi
Deliverable Nature	OA
Dissemination level	<i>Public</i>
Version	1.0
Revision	Final

1. Document Info

1.1. Authors

Author name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Maria Åkerman	VTT	maria.akerman@vtt.fi
Sarah McDonough, UAB	UAB	sarah.mcdonough@uab.cat
Chiara Gunella	UAB	chiara.gunella@uab.cat
Pilar Orero	UAB	pilar.orero@uab.cat
Marta Brescia Zapata	UAB	marta.zapata@uab.cat
Anna Matamala	UAB	anna.matamala@uab.cat
Sif Juhl Jacobsen	DemX (DBT)	sjj@demx.dk

1.2. Contributors

Contributor name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Loukas Katikas	EA	loukas.katikas@ea.gr
Teuvo Uusitalo	VTT	teuvo.uusitalo@vtt.fi
Zarrin Fatima	VTT	Zarrin.fatima@vtt.fi

1.3. Reviewers

Reviewers name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Manfred Mudelsee	CRA	climate-risk-analysis.com
Jaume Targa	4sfera	jaume.targa@4sfera.com

1.4. Document History

Version #	Author/s	Date	Changes
0.1	Maria Åkerman, Sarah McDonough, Chiara.Gunella, pilar Oreo, Marta Brescia Zapata, Anna Matamala	11.6.2024	Draft

0.2	Teuvo Uusitalo, Sif Jacobsen	21.6.2024	Draft for review
1.0	Maria Åkerman, Teuvo Uusitalo	28.6.2024	Final version

1.5. Document data

Keywords	<i>environmental citizenship, transformative pedagogy, citizen science, youth design assemblies, inclusion, accessibility, policy recommendation</i>
Editor address data	Name: Maria Åkerman Partner: VTT Technical Centre of Finland Address: P.O. Box 1000, FI-02044 VTT, Finland Email: maria.akerman@vtt.fi
Peer Review date	21.06.2024
Submission date	28.6.2024

1.6. Table of Contents

1. DOCUMENT INFO	1
1.1. AUTHORS	1
1.2. CONTRIBUTORS	1
1.3. REVIEWERS	1
1.4. DOCUMENT HISTORY	1
1.5. DOCUMENT DATA	2
1.6. TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
2. INTRODUCTION & OUTLOOK	4
3. THE OBJECTIVES OF THE POLICY BRIEF	6
4. TOWARDS TRANSFORMATIVE AND EMANCIPATORY PEDAGOGIES	7
5. DESIGNING ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION WITH YOUNG PEOPLE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE	10
6. LEAVING NO ONE BEHIND IN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION	14

2. Introduction & outlook

This document introduces the GreenSCENT policy recommendations and guidelines produced as part of Task 2.4 GreenSCENT Guide and Policy Recommendations. The recommendations are based on systematic collection of feedback from the consortium partners and participants engaged in GreenSCENT pilot and demonstration activities during the project. The feedback and continuous dialogue have enabled us to bring up the bottom-up perspective of teachers, instructors and European young people on the measures that should be taken at different levels of policy-making and in grass roots education to enhance environmental citizenship.

The generation of the policy recommendations

The formulation of policy recommendations and guidelines has been an iterative process. In addition to feedback surveys and interviews for WP6 impact assessment, the 1,5 years dialogue within the four Youth Design Assemblies (D2.2. & www.green-scent.eu/youth-assemblies/) has generated a rich and multi-voiced view on the objectives and wishes that teachers and students attach to sustainability education. In addition, we have also been able to identify frequently shared obstacles for action-oriented and transformative environmental education. The final policy recommendations and guidelines have been co-created during the first six months of the year 2024 with a survey on the key learnings of pilot activities in January 2024, an online workshop to clarify the key messages in February 2024 and a collection of input for justifying, concretising and validating the messages from consortium partners and participants of GreenSCENT activities in April – June 2024.

The contents of the policy recommendations

The final policy brief consists of three independent but interrelated parts which are all vital for enhancing environmental citizenship in education. The first part, ***Towards transformative and emancipatory pedagogies***, introduces the benefits of and obstacles for adopting action-oriented sustainability pedagogy from the teachers' and educators' perspective and presents recommendations for overcoming the obstacles. The second part, ***Designing Environmental Education for Young People with Young People*** emphasises the importance of involving European youth into dialogue on sustainability issues and in shaping environmental education to make it more meaningful and impactful. As such, it gives voice to the young participants of Youth Design Assemblies and suggests recommendations both for policy makers and teachers on how to engage young people in a fair, inclusive and productive way in dialogue and co-creation. Whereas the two first parts of the policy recommendations and guidelines arise directly from the experiences wishes and concerns of the grassroots actors and GreenSCENT demonstrators the third part, ***Leaving no one behind in environmental education***, introduces the perspective of GreenSCENT consortium partners on the vital importance of inclusion and accessibility in designing environmental education. This part of the policy brief suggests several measures for policy makers on how to promote inclusion and accessibility in education and provides concrete guidelines for instructors to address these issues in their everyday work.

Outlook

The GreenSCENT policy recommendations target decision-makers at regional, national and EU-level in education and research policy fields. They also offer practical guidelines for educators, instructors and those planning to establish Youth Design Assemblies. To effectively communicate with the intended audience, we have aimed to make our message clear and concise to read.

In the next phase, we will focus on the layout of the policy recommendations and guidelines in July 2024 to enhance readability and communication. The recommendations will be available on the GreenSCENT website, allowing dissemination as a comprehensive package or individually by topic for a specific audience. The final dissemination plan will be developed in August 2024.

3. The objectives of the policy brief

The European Green Deal has set up ambitious goals to overcome the threats that climate change and environmental degradation cause for humankind. The aim is to transform Europe into a resource-efficient circular economy with net zero climate emissions, diminishing pollution and restoration of biodiversity. Citizen engagement, particularly through environmental education, is crucial for innovating solutions and driving this transformation. Engaging citizens in acting upon sustainability challenges, innovating solutions and enhancing the transformation is necessary to reach these goals.

Environmental education is vital in equipping individuals with the capacity to address environmental challenges, thereby supporting active environmental citizenship for sustainability transformation. To reach this goal, teachers and schools must be supported in adopting pedagogical approaches that engage learners in sustainability actions across diverse contexts, motivating and empowering educators and students of all ages and socio-demographic backgrounds.

This document presents 1) policy recommendations for regional, national and EU level decision making in the fields of education and research policies and 2) concrete guidelines for educators and project managers to enhance inclusive and emancipatory environmental education in Europe, focusing on three key areas:

- 1. Supporting educators in a shift towards transformative and emancipatory pedagogies**
- 2. Designing environmental education for young people with young people**
- 3. Establishing practices for leaving no one behind in environmental education**

The recommendations are based on the findings of the EU Horizon 2020 funded GreenSCENT project (<https://www.green-scent.eu/>), which has created a holistic competence framework for environmental education and piloted and collected feedback on a variety of citizen-science based environmental education methods from teachers, instructors and engaged young people. This policy brief aims to bring up the bottom-up perspective and suggestions of these actors on the broader policy discussion.

In the following, we will present the three topics and introduce the arguments of why these issues are important for the creation of environmental citizenship in education. At the end of each section, we will introduce a set of targeted guidelines and policy recommendations for each of the themes.

4. Towards transformative and emancipatory pedagogies

Teachers require support to effectively address environmental challenges and empower students through action-oriented pedagogical approaches. Pedagogical tools must be diverse and adaptable to suit various educational contexts, considering e.g., regional disparities, available resources, and student demographics.

The key objective of education for environmental citizenship is to inspire sustainable actions by increasing environmental awareness, altering behaviours and creating sense of agency. For this to happen, educational programs and applied teaching methods should cultivate sustainability competencies among learners. In addition to providing substance knowledge on environmental issues, the utilisation of specific teaching methodologies that enhance the skills and capacities for transformative actions, forward-looking perspectives, collaborative decision-making and problem-solving are needed.

Shifting from 'package-based' approaches with teachers delivering information to competence-oriented education puts focus on learners acquiring the abilities for social action and pro-environmental behaviour. GreenSCENT project's findings suggest that sustainability competences can be developed through **transformative and emancipatory pedagogies** which both promote environmental awareness and ensure that learners with diverse backgrounds and acting in different contexts can participate in creating a sustainable future.

According to previous studies on Learning for sustainability (Gough 2005; Leicht et al., 2018), methods that foster sustainability competencies should be learner-centred and action-oriented. These methods may include:

- Collaborative real-world projects: Engaging in service-learning projects and campaigns on different sustainability topics.
- Vision-building exercises: Conducting future workshops, scenario analyses, utopian/dystopian storytelling, science-fiction thinking to explore sustainable futures.
- Complex systems analysis: Carrying out community-based research projects, case studies, modelling, and systems games to understand environmental dynamics.

Infobox 1: Examples of action-oriented methods:

GreenSCENT piloted several action-oriented citizen-science based pedagogical tools, for example: Air quality monitoring with GreenAir@School activity, Monitoring of microplastics, and Citizen journalism

More information can be found here: <https://www.green-scent.eu/>

Identified obstacles for educators to adopt action-oriented and transformative environmental pedagogies

Sustainability education presents unique challenges due to its complexity. Teachers' abilities and resources to facilitate activities on this topic vary widely. A critical issue is the limited availability of adaptable pedagogical tools, such as citizen science methods, for different age groups. This, coupled with insufficient time dedicated for creating collaboration networks for citizen science activities (see the teacher's experience in the infobox below) and lack of technical and financial support, hampers the prospects for equitable sustainability learning throughout Europe.

Infobox 2: Teacher's experiences of facilitating children's air quality monitoring activities

First, we discussed in the classroom of how dosimeters could be installed on private property (with the owner's approval) or public property (with the Mayor's Office approval). We wrote an email to the Water Quality Agency, and we received a positive answer right away allowing us to install dosimeters on their units. We also wrote an email to the Mayor's Office to be allowed to install dosimeters on public light posts, but we never received an answer. Weeks later, we called the Mayor's Office and talked to the representative in the specific department- he knew about the email and invited us to stop by and collect a written approval. When the school representative stopped by, he was not handed one and they did not seem pleased that we chose main streets for location of dosimeters and encouraged us to choose parks and the valley of the river. They were explained that we wanted to measure the air quality on streets which kids use when coming to school; the answer was delayed (election season) and we still don't have it.

However, we received an email from the Ministry of Environment containing a letter that acknowledged our request, our involvement with GreenSCENT and our local intentions, and they gave us a written consent to install dosimeters on any of their units (which we had already received from the local Water Quality Agency).

I am quite convinced that with this letter we could have received the Mayor's Office approval as well but at that time the dosimeters were already installed on private properties.

The students were proud that we had received a letter from such an important national institution.

According to GreenSCENT findings, teachers identify the following obstacles for adopting competence – and action-oriented pedagogies:

- **Resource Constraints:** Teachers often lack the necessary resources and support to implement action-oriented methods building on integrative communication between the class and outside world.
- **Community Engagement:** Methods involving community participation, such as student-led local environmental monitoring projects, require significant time investment to establish collaborative networks with local governmental and non-governmental organisations.
- **Technical Support:** There is a lack of technical support for teachers in adopting digital pedagogical tools for citizen science. The schools may have the needed technical devices and software, but without dedicated time to prepare the citizen science activities teachers are not able to adopt the methods.

- **Research Collaboration:** The networks for collaboration with research organisations that could support citizen-science activities are underdeveloped.
- **Tools and Methods of Engagement:** Digital tools for collecting and analysing monitoring data or exchanging knowledge between students and schools are not user-friendly. Sustainability issues addressed by current pedagogical tools may not resonate with students' experience or be age-appropriate, affecting their motivation.

Recommendations for policy measures to support action-oriented, emancipatory and transformative pedagogies:

To facilitate action-oriented sustainability education, fostering effective collaboration between schools and the broader community is essential. Furthermore, aligning pedagogical insights from citizen science approaches with scientific goals requires systematic collaboration between schools and universities. We propose the following measures:

- **Support for Environmental Education Ecosystems:** Provide funding and support for establishing environmental education ecosystems that link schools with universities and research organisations. This will encourage project-based collaboration, provide schools with access to novel research tools and equipment, increase universities' understanding of teachers' pedagogical needs, and expand the adoption of citizen-science methods in environmental education, even in areas without regional research facilities.
- **Funding for Educational Blueprints:** Allocate resources to develop a hands-on blueprint for a community-oriented whole school approach to sustainability education. This blueprint should offer guidelines for building educational programs which allocate time for action-oriented sustainability education and connect learning with relevant community issues. Incorporating sustainability topics into the curriculum through hands – and minds – on activities will support teachers in organising learning activities and give students opportunities to engage in tangible sustainability actions.
- **Knowledge Exchange Programme:** Establish a funding programme to facilitate the exchange of Best Practices for action-oriented sustainability education between schools. This will promote peer learning among teachers and across different European regions.

5. Designing environmental education with young people for young people

To enhance democratic environmental citizenship, there is a need to create spaces where young people can actively contribute to sustainability discussions and actions based on their opinions and ideas. Involving young people in the development of environmental education enhances its impact and relevance, encouraging student participation and co-creation.

Co-creation is a frequently used method for developing products or processes together with stakeholders. Engaging students in improving learning materials by providing their ideas, experiences, and feedback has also been applied in higher education (Cook-Sather et al., 2014; Finlayson, 2014). These experiences have shown that youth involvement can be a powerful tool to create educational resources, particularly when aiming to support the active citizenship of young people (Sjöström & Eilks 2020).

Infobox 3: Insights of young people on why it matters to engage youth in shaping sustainability education

“Young people are the ones who need to learn about green competencies because it is our future. Something so important should not be ignored, but put on blast, so that solutions can be put in place.”

“I care and feel worried about the climate crisis and think it’s important to discuss how we can make a change. It’s an important issue and concerns everyone.”

“They (young people) are aware of how young people like to learn and what they find interesting and relevant. Therefore, in order to make the process effective towards young people, young people need to have a say in how it should be.”

GreenSCENT successfully piloted the Youth Design Assembly method involving 56 young people aged 14 – 24 from seven European countries in a dynamic review and feedback process. Participants from Denmark, Finland, Greece, Italy, Romania, Serbia, and Spain discussed, evaluated, and gave feedback to co-create sustainability education from curriculum design to individual courses and specific pedagogical tools (more information at www.green-scent.eu/youth-assemblies) This approach has demonstrated the benefits of youth participation in shaping education for sustainable future (eg., Burmeister et al. 2024).

Youth Design Assembly’s findings and feedback show that involving students in shaping and co-creating environmental education is an impactful approach to generate novel ideas and enhance the relevance of education for young people. Engaged students generated many concrete suggestions for new pedagogical tools and suggested valuable

enhancements to existing ones. Our feedback and evaluation data underscores the effectiveness of this engagement in enhancing students' environmental agency (see the infobox 4). Recognising that young people are often underrepresented in participatory processes, targeted efforts are needed to ensure their equal involvement in decision-making. These insights highlight the transformative potential of student engagement in shaping a more meaningful and impactful environmental education.

Infobox 4. Feedback of participants involved in GreenSCENT Youth Design Assemblies

STUDENT FEEDBACK

- "It made us feel helpful, because our suggestions were used. We are also happy and excited to see the end result. The app could be useful if implemented right."
- "I feel angry that so little is happening in relation to green change. Being part of a [Youth Assembly] has shown me how a lot of individuals and companies are doing their best. However, on a larger scale, we are seeing little to no difference, which is very demotivating."
- "Seeing the results made me feel like I have contributed to the start of a greener Europe"

MODERATORS' FEEDBACK

- "The participants expressed how the co-creation workshop and the ideas generated gave them hope."
- "We are beyond happy to see how the Youth Assemblies enable the young participants to recognize themselves as changemakers"
- "Becoming aware of the value the participants bring to the table is an important step towards empowerment, and hopefully they can use it to inspire other youths."

Summary of the key benefits of youth engagement young people in shaping environmental education:

- **Relevance and Motivation:** Student-centred educational approaches can significantly increase learning motivation. Co-creating educational resources with students ensures the curriculum and activities are engaging and pertinent.
- **Early Involvement:** Students' early participation in curriculum and course design makes it possible to identify opportunities and shape implementations for better support and positive engagement.
- **Mutual Learning:** Dialogue and co-creation support mutual inspiration and learning, provided the right means and platforms are available.
- **Community Engagement:** Mutual learning, inspiration, and cultural encounters can help to foster a sense of community and engagement.
- **Emotion and Action:** Emotions and motivation are crucial for action. Science, facts, and rationality seldom lead to action on their own.

Recommendations for policy measures to support student – centred methods and dialogue in shaping environmental education:

Student involvement in curriculum and course development is a promising, yet underutilised approach to enrich environmental education and support environmental citizenship of young people. However, a knowledge gap exists among schools, educators and policymakers regarding effective engagement methods and best practices for involving young people in dialogue. This gap, coupled with scepticism from decision makers and educators, can hinder the adoption of co-creation and dialogic methods in shaping education.

To address these challenges, we recommend the following policy measures:

- **Establish Youth Design Assemblies:** Create Local, National and European Youth Design Assemblies to promote sustainability dialogue between young people and decision-makers. Youth Design Assemblies can be used to generate ideas and recommendations for specific policy topics, to inform and validate policies and to develop and improve the content of environmental education framework or to develop the framework itself.
- **Awareness Campaign:** Launch an information campaign to highlight the benefits of youth design assemblies in social dialogue, sustainability decision making and in designing sustainability education for young people. The campaign should also include Blueprints and training for organising Youth Design Assemblies.

Guidelines for organising Youth Assemblies in a fair and inclusive manner

In addition to designing education, Youth Assemblies can serve various other purposes as well, such as idea generation and policy recommendations and validation. Therefore, they can be arranged in diverse ways and should always be tailored to the specific objective. Here are some general guidelines to guarantee a fair and impactful design of Youth Assemblies:

- **Objective and scope definition:** Clearly define the purpose of the Youth Design Assembly. Determine who the participants will be (age) and consider whether they should be experts on the topic or laypeople. Establish the assembly's scope.
- **Content and process overview:** Plan the number of meetings, identify the facilitators, and decide on the platforms and tools to be used. Consider whether the Youth will convene in person, online or both. Outline the topics and decide how much should be fixed from the start and how much will the participants be able to influence the process and the content.
- **Participant recruitment:** Select participants relevant to the assembly's scope and strive for inclusivity considering age, gender, sociodemographic background, regional diversity, and representation of underrepresented and vulnerable groups.
- **Safe and inclusive dialogue space:** Allocate enough time initially for participants to get to know each other and the topic. Ensure that those uncomfortable with speaking in plenary sessions have alternative ways to express their opinions. Assist participants in developing a code of conduct that sets the norms for the Youth Design Assembly.
- **Co-design of the process:** Maintain a flexible process plan and actively involve participants in co-designing the final process, methods and content.
- **Face-to-face connection:** If possible, organise at least one in-person meeting at the start to foster personal connections among participants.
- **Respecting young participants:** Treat the Youth Design Assembly with utmost respect and seriousness. Avoid overruling the decisions and wishes of the young participants.
- **Participant motivation:** Encourage and support participants' ideas, allowing for process flexibility to allow new ideas to evolve.
- **Creating impact:** Consider how to bring the Youth Design Assembly ideas out to the real world. Support participants in further work on the topic by facilitating network connections, linking them with relevant organisations or individuals, and providing recognition through certificates or personal recommendations for their work in the Youth Assembly.

6. Leaving no one behind in environmental education

Investing in inclusive environmental education programmes and practices is vital to overcome barriers (physical, systemic and digital) to environmental education and promote climate justice

This section of this policy report focuses on ensuring inclusion and accessibility in environmental education, aiming to leave no one behind in environmental education. Inclusion is a multidimensional concept that refers to the practice of making spaces, both physical and digital, open to a diverse range of people from different backgrounds, identities and abilities (see United Nations, 2016). Within the context of environmental education, inclusion refers to the ability of students and educators to be able to access and understand information, educational resources and programmes on and about the environment, regardless of format (physical or digital). The key to achieving inclusion lies in ensuring the accessibility and usability of the materials, tools and educational programmes developed.

Accessibility refers to the extent to which a product or service can be used by a diverse range of people to achieve a specified goal in a specific context (ISO 26800, ISO/TR 9241-100, and ISO/TR2241). "Usability" refers to the combination of the effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction with which specified users achieve specified goals in particular environments ([ISO 9241-11 standard](#), 2018). Tied to the concept of usability is the principle of Universal Design, which refers to the design of products, environments, programmes and services that are usable by everyone, to the greatest extent possible, without the need for adaptation or specialised design. Universal Design does not exclude assistive devices for particular groups or persons with disabilities where necessary.

Why is inclusion and accessibility vital for environmental education?

- Environmental education has come to be recognised as a pragmatic response to the issues posed by the environmental crisis (Padmanabhan et al., 2017, p.722) and has taken shape against the backdrop of increased political initiatives to promote climate resilience with the full participation of all, including those from a diverse range of background, abilities and identities (United Nations Committee for Development Policy, 2018).
- The United Nations (UN) foregrounded the importance of education in combating the adverse effects of the environmental crisis in their Decade of Education for Sustainable Development initiative in which they emphasised the role of education in changing behaviours (see also Buckler & Creech, 2014).
- Tied to this aim is the desire for environmental education to be available to all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, ethnicity, religion, economic or social status (see United Nations' Sustainability Goals 4.5, 2015).
- This emphasis on inclusivity and diversity is particularly crucial because the effects of climate change are not uniformly felt across and within societies.
- Social disparity plays a significant role in amplifying climate vulnerability, particularly for those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds and those with disabilities.

Currently, an estimated 15% of the global population has a disability (World Health

Organisation), with people with disabilities “disproportionately vulnerable to natural hazards primarily as a consequence of social disadvantage, poverty and structural exclusion” (Hemingway & Priestly 2014: 8).

- Enabling people to make informed decisions about the development and conservation of their environment through inclusive environmental education is key to addressing the challenges of the climate crisis (Boyes & Stanisstreet, 2012, Sunassee et al. 2021).

Recommendations for policymakers to support inclusion in environmental education:

- **Funding and resources:** allocate specific grants for developing educational materials and training programs that ensure accessible and inclusive environmental education. Funding is often a major barrier to implementing inclusive practices, as specialised materials and programmes can be costly. Research shows that targeted financial support can facilitate significant advancements in educational inclusivity and accessibility (Armstrong et al., 2011).
- **Training programmes:** invest in training opportunities that equip instructors with the skills to incorporate inclusive and accessible practices.
- **Curriculum guidelines:** establish clear guidelines that embed inclusivity into the environmental education curriculum at primary, secondary and third level.
- **Mandatory accessible environmental education:** introduce compulsory accessible environmental education at primary and secondary level, tailoring it to the needs of students.
- **Community partnerships:** encourage partnerships between schools, higher educational institutions and local communities to co-create spaces of dialogue and exchange.
- **Partnerships with organisations dedicated to diversity and inclusion:** encourage partnerships between schools, higher educational institutions and organisations dedicated to improving diversity and inclusion of marginalised groups.
- **Technology and accessibility:** ensure that digital educational tools are accessible to all students, including those with disabilities, offering them in multiple formats including digital, audio and braille. Learning materials should also be easy to read.

Example

The European Accessibility Act (2019) is a reference document for accessibility, which can be accessed [here](#).

Recommendations for educators and instructors:

Educators design curricula, while instructors deliver the teaching. We recognise that these roles may sometimes overlap. Therefore, the following recommendations are aimed at both educators and instructors.

- **Ensure accessibility in the classroom:** ensure that all physical and digital learning environments are accessible to students and educators with disabilities. This includes classrooms, educational materials, and online resources that comply with international accessibility standards. Schools should ensure their facilities, including classrooms and outdoor areas, comply with the [European Accessibility Act](#), featuring wheelchair-accessible pathways and accommodating classroom designs to support various mobility and sensory needs. Likewise, digital resources need to conform to the [European Standard EN 301 549 on "Accessibility requirements for ICT products and services"](#) and [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(WCAG\)](#). This includes optimising online materials with alternative text for images, video captions, and keyboard-navigable websites, ensuring that students with visual, auditory, or motor impairments have equal access to educational content.
- **Include climate justice awareness:** incorporating climate justice into environmental education involves highlighting how climate change disproportionately affects the world's most vulnerable groups. It is crucial to raise awareness of the diverse impacts on different communities and to emphasise the importance of avoiding generalisations. Studies by Mohai et al. (2009) and Sultana (2022) illustrate how environmental challenges have historically impacted marginalised communities. Recognising these disparities supports a comprehensive understanding of climate issues.
- **Include diverse ways of knowing:** educators should expand their teaching to include perspectives beyond Eurocentric views by incorporating diverse methods of understanding environmental and climate issues. This approach can help students appreciate the valuable insights offered by different knowledge systems. As Rabe (2023) suggests, incorporating indigenous and local knowledge can reveal various ecological relationships and sustainability practices. This helps students recognise that there are multiple valid approaches to supporting the planet.
- **Address climate anxiety:** research highlights the prevalence of climate anxiety among young people and the need for educational strategies to address it (Hickman et al., 2021; Marks et al., 2021; Kurth & Pihkala, 2022). The curriculum should include elements that help students understand and manage climate-related anxiety. Positive actions and coping strategies can empower students to deal with their concerns constructively.
- **Monitor and evaluate** implement regular assessments of educational programmes to ensure they meet inclusivity goals (Sibanda & Mathwasa, 2020). Feedback mechanisms should be in place to assess the effectiveness of accessibility measures, gathering feedback from students, parents and educators to suggest improvements.

Example

This book chapter presents a case study of integrating emerging technology to promote accessibility and sustainability in the classroom:

McDonagh, Sarah, and Marta Brescia Zapata. 2023. 'Combining XR, Accessibility, and Sustainability in the Classroom: Results of an Exploratory Study'. In Bridging the XR Technology-to-Practice Gap, 67–79. AACE2023.

References

Armstrong, D., Armstrong, A. C., & Spandagou, I. 2011. Inclusion: By choice or by chance?. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 15(1), 29–39. doi: 10.1080/13603116.2010.496192.

Boyes, E., and Martin Stanisstreet. 2012. 'Environmental Education for Behaviour Change: Which Actions Should Be Targeted?' *International Journal of Science Education* 34 (10): 1591–1614.

Buckler, C., and Heather Creech. 2014. 'Shaping the Future We Want: UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development; Final Report'. Paris: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

Burmeister, D. Nielsen, I. Jacobsen, S., Jorgensen, M. (2024). Youth Assemblies: Youth engagement for Green Learning and Action. In McDonagh, S. et al (Eds.). *European Green deal in Education*. Routledge, in press.

Gough, A. (2005). Sustainable Schools: Renovating Educational Processes, *Applied Environmental Education and Communication*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15330150500302205>

Finlayson, C. C. (2014). Using focus groups to enhance student voice: A work-in-progress exploration of student learning experiences in large classes. *Enhancing the Learner Experience in Higher Education*, 6(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.14234/elehe.v6i1.92>

Hemingway, L., and Mark Priestley. 2014. 'Natural Hazards, Human Vulnerability and Disabling Societies: A Disaster for Disabled People?' *Review of Disability Studies: An International Journal* 2 (3).

Hickman, C., Marks, E., Pihkala, P., Clayton, S., Lewandowski, R. E., Mayall, E. E., Wray, B., Mellor, C., & van Susteren, L. (2021). Climate anxiety in children and young people and their beliefs about government responses to climate change: a global survey. *The Lancet. Planetary health*, 5(12), e863–e873. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(21\)00278-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00278-3)

International Organization for Standardization. 2011. 'ISO 26800:2011. Ergonomics - General Approach, Principles and Concepts'.

International Organization for Standardization. 2018. 'ISO 9241-11:2018. Ergonomics of human-system interaction, Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts'.

International Organization for Standardization. 2021. 'ISO/TR 22411:2021. Ergonomics data for use in the application of ISO/IEC Guide 71:2014'.

International Organization for Standardization. 2023. 'ISO/TR 9241-100:2023. Ergonomics of Human-System Interaction'.

Kurth, C., & Pihkala, P. 2022. Eco-anxiety: What it is and why it matters. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 981814.

Leicht, A. and Won, J.B. (eds). 2018. *Issues and trends in education for sustainable development*. UNESCO Publishing.

Marks, E., Hickman, C., Pihkala, P., Clayton, S., Lewandowski, E. R., Mayall, E. E., ... & van Susteren, L. (2021). Young people's voices on climate anxiety, government betrayal and moral injury: A global phenomenon. *Government Betrayal and Moral injury: a global phenomenon*.

McDonagh, S., and Marta Brescia Zapata. 2023. 'Combining XR, Accessibility, and Sustainability in the Classroom: Results of an Exploratory Study'. In *Bridging the XR Technology-to-Practice Gap*, 67–79. AACE2023.

Mohai, P., Pellow, D., & Roberts, J. T. (2009). Environmental justice. *Annual review of environment and resources*, 34, 405-430.

Padmanabhan, J., Aradhana Borthakur, and Kunjana Mittal. 2017. 'Environmental Awareness among Teachers and Students in Higher Education'. *Educational Quest: An International Journal of Education and Applied Social Science*, 8 (3): 721–26.

Rabe, C. (2023). Toward "Resistance and Re-visioning": Exploring the Integration of Community Partnerships and Decolonial Field Methods in an Undergraduate Environmental Justice Program. *Environmental Justice*.

Sultana, F. (2022). Critical climate justice. *The Geographical Journal*, 188(1), 118-124.

Sibanda, L., & Mathwasa, J. (2020). Promoting Inclusivity Through Quality Assessment in Rural Secondary Schools. *The Education Systems of Africa*, 1-18.

Sjöström, J., & Eilks, I. (2020). The Bildung Theory—From von Humboldt to Klafki and Beyond. In B. Akpan & T. J. Kennedy (Eds.), *Science Education in Theory and Practice: An Introductory Guide to Learning Theory* (pp. 55–67). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43620-9_5

Sunassee, A., Chandradeo Bokhoree, and Andrew Patrizio. 2021. 'Student's Empathy for the Environment through Eco-Art Place-Based Education: A Review'. *Ecologies*, no. 2, 214–47.

United Nations. 2015. 'Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development'. United Nations.
https://www.un.org/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=A/RES/70/1&Lang=E.

United Nations. 2016. 'Leaving No One behind: The Imperative of Inclusive Development, Report on the World Social Situation, 2016'. New York: Department of Economic and Social Affairs, United Nations.

United Nations Committee for Development Policy. 2018. 'Leaving No One Behind'. United Nations.